

A COMPARISON OF THREE SHEAR TEST METHODS FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

H. Ho, M. Y. Tsai, J. Morton
Department of Engineering Science and Mechanics
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
Blacksburg VA 24061-0219

and

G. L. Farley
US Army Aerostructures Directorate
NASA Langley Research Center
Hampton VA 23665-5225

ABSTRACT

The performance of three popular shear tests - the 10° off-axis, the $\pm 45^\circ$ tension and the Iosipescu specimen tested in the modified Wyoming fixture - is evaluated using a graphite-epoxy composite material system. A comparison of the shear stress-strain response for each test method is made using conventional strain gage instrumentation and moire interferometry. The uniformity and purity of the strain fields in the test sections of the specimens are discussed, and the shear responses obtained from each test are presented and compared.

KEYWORDS: Shear; Test Method; Moire Interferometry; Fibers, Graphite; Matrix, Epoxy.

1. INTRODUCTION

The in-plane shear modulus G_{12} of a unidirectional composite material is a fundamental parameter for the elastic characterization of composite laminates. For the purposes of design, the shear stress-strain response and the shear strength are also required. Of the many available test methods for determining the shear response of composite materials, Lee and Munro [1] have ranked the 10° off-axis [2-5], the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test [3,6,7] and the Iosipescu test method [8-15] most highly.

For the shear response obtained from each test method strain gages are used to determine the shear strain averaged over the area of the specimen underneath the strain gages. The shear stress is taken to be the average shear stress across the specimen test section. Recent comparisons [12, 14] of the 10° off-axis, the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test and the Iosipescu test method for graphite-epoxy composites have shown that each test method does not produce identical shear responses. The discrepancy between the responses obtained from the three test methods applied to the same material has been ascribed to the lack of uniformity of the strain fields in the test sections of the specimens for each test method [12,14]. The differences in the shear strengths obtained in each test method is thought to be due to the

strain field nonuniformity and the varying degrees of purity of the shear as a result of the test method and the material properties [15].

In the present investigation shear tests are performed on graphite-epoxy composite specimens instrumented with strain gages on one surface and moire interferometry was used to determine the strains on the opposite surface. As well as allowing a comparison of the strains on the opposite surfaces of the specimens, moire interferometry provided a means for assessing the purity and uniformity of the shear strain fields in the specimen test sections.

2. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

2.1 Moire Interferometry Moire interferometry [16] is an optical method of measuring the in-plane surface displacement components (u,v) of a loaded specimen. The technique employs a high frequency crossed-line grating which is attached to the surface of the specimen and deforms with the specimen surface. The interference of two coherent light beams diffracted from the deformed specimen produces moire fringe patterns corresponding to the u and v fields. The sensitivity f of the technique is determined by the frequency of the specimen grating, the wavelength of the light, λ , and the optical arrangement. The basic equation is,

$$f = \frac{2}{\lambda} \sin \alpha \quad (1)$$

where α is the angle between the incident beam and the first order diffracted beam. The displacement components u and v are obtained from the fringe order N_x and N_y by

$$u = \frac{1}{f} N_x \quad \text{and} \quad v = \frac{1}{f} N_y \quad (2)$$

and the in-plane strains by

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_x &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{f} \frac{\partial N_x}{\partial x} \\ \epsilon_y &= \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{f} \frac{\partial N_y}{\partial y} \\ \gamma_{xy} &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{f} \left(\frac{\partial N_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial N_y}{\partial x} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The crossed-line diffraction gratings that were applied to the surface of the specimens had a frequency of 1200 lines/mm, and covered the width of each specimen and extended approximately 30 mm lengthwise. The three mirror interferometer which was used in the moire experiments was developed by Czarnek [17], and gave a fringe pattern sensitivity of $0.417 \mu\text{m}$ per fringe ($f = 2400$ lines/ mm) .

2.2 Materials and Specimen Dimensions A unidirectional 20-ply graphite-epoxy panel was fabricated from AS4/3501-6 prepregged tape. The 10° off-axis, $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test and Iosipescu specimen dimensions used in the experimental program are shown in Figure 1 which also contains details of the strain gage rosettes and locations of the moire gratings. The Iosipescu specimens were prepared with the fibers oriented in either the 0° and 90° directions, as indicated in Figure 1c. The dimensions of the Iosipescu specimens were those required for the modified Wyoming test fixture which was used in the investigation [10,15].

2.3 Specimen Testing The instrumented specimens were tested in a conventional screw driven test machine. The three-mirror interferometer was positioned in front of the specimen. Before applying load to the specimen, the interferometer was tuned to provide no-load (null field) fringe patterns. The null field fringe patterns consisted of one fringe or less across the field of view. Load was then applied to the specimen until a predetermined value was obtained. Under constant loading, u and v fringe patterns were recorded photographically. A set of patterns was also obtained with rigid body rotation introduced. The shear strain γ_{xy-r} due to the rigid body rotation is given by

$$\gamma_{xy-r} = \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) = 0. \quad (4)$$

The rotation can be adjusted to cancel out the cross derivative term, $\partial u/\partial y$, of the u field. Therefore, the v field (with rotation) contains all the shear information in the uniform region of the test section. This technique is known as applying a carrier pattern of rotation and is a convenience for fringe pattern interpretation and data reduction. This test procedure was repeated at numerous load levels until the fringe patterns became too dense to analyze.

2.4 Data Reduction The strain gage data were recorded using a computer controlled data acquisition system. For each of the different shear specimens, the *average* shear stress was calculated in the appropriate coordinate system. Strain gage data were reduced to shear strains at the center of the test section.

For the 10° off-axis specimen:

$$\tau_{12}^{ave} = 0.171 \frac{P}{A} \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma_{12} = 0.342 (\epsilon_y - \epsilon_x) - 0.940 \gamma_{xy}$$

where P is the applied load and A is the specimen cross-sectional area. Subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the fiber and in-plane normal to the fiber directions, respectively.

For the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test specimen:

$$\tau_{12}^{ave} = 0.5 \frac{P}{A} \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma_{12} = (\epsilon_x - \epsilon_y)$$

For the Iosipescu shear test:

$$\tau_{12}^{ave} = \frac{1}{h} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \tau_{xy} dy \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma_{12} = \gamma_{xy} = (\epsilon_{SG1} - \epsilon_{SG2})$$

where h is the distance between the notch roots.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 10° Off-axis Test The moire fringe data were used to determine shear strains over a region equivalent to that of the strain gage rosette which was attached to the opposite face of the specimen. A comparison of the shear stress-strain response on the front and back faces of the specimen is shown in Figure 2. Typical moire fringe patterns for the 10° off-axis specimen are shown in Figure 3. The data in Figure 3a indicate that the horizontal displacement field $u(x,y)$ on the surface of the specimen is uniform with some highly localized nonuniform component. That is, the fringes are generally straight, parallel and uniformly spaced. The nonuniformity is thought to be due to the imperfect fiber/tow distribution. The moire data in Figure 3b represent the vertical component of displacement $v(x,y)$ on the surface of the specimen. The v -displacement field is not uniform.

The normal and shear strains across the width of the 10° off-axis specimen were computed from the moire data using Equations 3 and transformed to the material axis system 1-2. The strain distributions are presented in Figure 4 for three locations, $y=0$, the horizontal center-line of the specimen, and $y=\pm w$, where w is the width of the specimen. The normal strain ϵ_1 is uniform across most of the specimen but there is a variation of about 25% between the strains values for the three horizontal lines along which the data were obtained. The normal strains ϵ_2 vary significantly across the section and with the location y . At the center of the specimen the Poisson's ratio ν_{12} is approximately 0.34. The shear strains γ_{12} are not uniform in the region covered by the moire grating. There are large variations in γ_{12} from one edge of the specimen to the other and between the three y locations. At $y=+w$, the variation in γ_{12} across the width of the specimen is 16% while at $y=0$ and $y=-w$, the variations are 12% and 9% respectively. The variation of averaged γ_{12} at $y=0$ and $y=\pm w$ is 3.8%. The ratio of the normal strain ϵ_2 to the shear strain γ_{12} of 0.5 is relatively large at the center of the specimen, suggesting that failure of the specimen will be under mixed mode conditions.

3.2 $\pm 45^\circ$ Tensile Test The shear stress-strain responses based on the strain gage and moire data are shown in Figure 5. The moire fringe patterns are shown in Figure 6. The horizontal component of the surface displacement field $u(x,y)$ consists of a uniform component together with a nonuniform displacement in bands at 45° to the loading direction. A nonuniform displacement associated with the free edges of the specimen is observed. The vertical component of the surface displacement field $v(x,y)$ is represented by closely spaced almost horizontal fringes in Figure 6b. There is also a nonuniform component of displacement associated with the surface fibers but it is not so apparent as that in the u -displacement field, Figure 6a. The uniform component of the displacement field can be removed optically [16]. This technique was used to produce the moire pattern shown in Figure 7 in which the nonuniform component of the v -displacement field can be clearly correlated with the fiber directions. The bands of relatively large deformation are thought to be associated with resin rich regions between the tows used in the fabrication of the prepregged graphite-epoxy tape.

The strains were determined from the moire fringe patterns using Equations 3 and transformed to obtain the components in the material coordinate system 1-2. The normal and shear strain distributions across the width w of the specimen are presented for two horizontal lines, $y=0$ and $y=0.5w$, in Figure 8. The normal strains ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are quite uniform across the specimen width for both values of y . As expected, the normal strains are equal. The presence of the free-edge effect is also apparent in the normal strain distributions. The shear strain γ_{12} distribution does appear to vary with y , Figure 8. The difference between the shear strains at the center of the specimens for the two values of y is about 10%. It should be noted that strain gage rosettes would give shear strains averaged over the area of the strain gage rosette so that the shear strains determined from strain gages would differ by about 5% at the center of the specimen for the two y values. The differences are a result of the material nonuniformity on the scale of the fiber tow.

3.3 Iosipescu Shear Test Two fiber orientations 0° and 90° were tested. The moire and strain gage data were used to obtain the shear stress-strain responses shown in Figures 9 and 10 for the 0° and 90° specimens, respectively. It is apparent that the front and back face responses are the same for

the 0° specimen but are quite different for the 90° specimen. This observation was used to deduce that the 90° specimen was prone to twisting [15], so that the shear strain on each face was a combination of the shear strains due to the applied shear force and torque on the specimen resulting from the fixture and the fiber orientation. On one face the effects add together, on the other they subtract, so that the average of the front and back face responses can be used. It should be noted that the difference between the front and back face response is systematic; the shear strains determined on the face farthest away from the fixture linear bearing, the front face, are always higher than those on the back face for the same applied load. This observation has important implications for the values of the shear moduli determined with specimens tested in the 90° configuration since it is common practice to use only one strain gage rosette, and it is probable that the strain gage rosette would be located on the front face of the specimen.

Typical moire fringe patterns for the 0° specimen are shown in Figure 11. The horizontal displacement field $u(x,y)$ is represented in Figure 11a. The very low fringe gradients in the horizontal (x) direction are consistent with the high bending stiffness of the specimen with the 0° fiber orientation. It should be noted that there is also a nonuniform component of displacement apparent in the fringe pattern in Figure 11a. This is discussed in greater detail in [18]. A pure and uniform shear field in the test section of the specimen would be represented in the vertical displacement field as a series of uniformly spaced vertical straight contours. In Figure 11b it is shown that the fringes are S-shaped so that there is some normal strain ϵ_y (ϵ_2) in the test section due to the proximity of the applied loads to the test section [15,18,19]. It has been shown [15,19] that this load proximity effect in the 0° specimen causes the magnitudes of the strains in gages SG1 and SG2, Figure 1c, to be different but does not affect the shear strain calculation.

The moire fringe patterns for the 90° specimen are shown in Figure 12. The horizontal displacement field $u(x,y)$, represented by the fringe pattern in Figure 12a, does contain significant bending strains which are to be expected from this fiber orientation which is characterized by a low extensional stiffness E_x . The vertical displacement field $v(x,y)$, represented by the fringe pattern in Figure 12b, corresponds to pure and uniform shear in a region at the center of the test section.

3.4 Comparison of Shear Stress-Strain Responses Typical shear stress-strain responses for the graphite-epoxy specimens tested in the 10° off-axis, the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile and the 0° and 90° Iosipescu methods are presented in Figure 13a. Since the tests are performed on the same materials it would be expected that each method should give the same response. It is apparent in Figure 13a that the responses are not the same and that the shear moduli obtained from the tests will be quite different. Even after allowing for the twisting of the 90° Iosipescu specimen (by taking the average of the front and back surface shear strains) the shear modulus appears to be significantly lower than that in the other tests. The difference between the responses can be attributed to the nonuniformity of the shear fields in the various tests. It should be noted that the shear stress-strain response is presented as the average shear stress across the specimen test section plotted against the shear strain at some area under the strain gage rosette.

Correction factors [12,15,19] have been suggested to allow for the nonuniformity of the shear strain fields in the 10° off-axis and the Iosipescu specimens by estimating average shear strain corresponding to the measured (local) shear strain. Unfortunately, these correction factors depend upon the material orthotropy ratio and, to a much lesser extent, upon the shear modulus itself. When the appropriate correction factors are applied to the experimentally determined shear strains the corrected responses, shown in Figure 13b, are obtained. The effect of these correction factors is to bring the responses of the 10° off-axis, the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile and the 0° & 90° Iosipescu specimens very close together, at least in the initial stages of the response where linear behavior was assumed for the calculation of the correction factors. The difference between the responses is consistent with the degree of nonuniformity of the material, as documented by the moire experiments.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Moire interferometry has been used to determine the surface displacement fields in 10° off-axis, $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile and 0° and 90° Iosipescu graphite-epoxy specimens. Comparisons of the moire data on one face of the specimens with data from a strain gage rosette on the opposite face have been made. It has been shown that the shear stress-strain responses obtained by instrumenting only one face of the 90° Iosipescu specimen could give erroneous results. The $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile and 0° Iosipescu specimens did not suffer from front to back face shear strain variations. Correction factors could be applied to bring all responses together, within the limits of the material uniformity, which was itself documented in the moire fringe patterns.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work reported here was supported by the US Army Aerostructures Directorate under NASA Research Grant NAG-1-1053. The authors would also like to express their gratitude to Drs. Robert Czamek and Joosik Lee of the Engineering Science and Mechanics Department at VPI&SU for their assistance with the moire experiments.

6. REFERENCES

1. S. Lee and M. Munro, Composites, **17** (1), 13, (1986).
2. C. C. Chamis and J. H. Sinclair, Experimental Mechanics, **17** (9), 339, (1977).
3. C. C. Chiao, R.L. Moore and T.T. Chiao, Composites, **8** (3), 161, (1977).
4. M. J. Pindera and C. T. Herakovich, Experimental Mechanics, **26**(1), 103, (1986).
5. N. J. Pagano and J. C. Halpin, J. Composite Materials, **2** (1), 18, (1968).
6. P. H. Petit, ASTM STP 460, 83, (1969)
7. B. W. Rosen, J. Composite Materials, **6**, 552, (1972).
8. N. Iosipescu, J. Materials, **2** (3), 537, (1967).
9. D. E. Walrath and D. F. Adams, Experimental Mechanics, **23** (1), 105, (1983).
10. D. F. Adams and D. E. Walrath, Experimental Mechanics, 113, (1987).

11. D. F. Adams and D. E. Walrath, J. Composite Materials, 21, 494, (1987).
12. M. J. Pindera, G. Choksi, J. S. Hidde and C. T. Herakovich, Composite Materials, 21, 1164, (1987).
13. M. G. Abdallah and H. E. Gascoigne, ASTM STP 1003, 2, 231, (1989).
14. S. Lee, M. Munro and R. F. Scott, Composites, 21(6), 495, (1990)
15. J. Morton, H. Ho, M.Y. Tsai and G.L. Farley, submitted to J. Composite Materials.
16. J. Guild, Theory of Moire Fringes, Oxford at the Clarendon Press, (1956).
17. R. Czarnek, New Methods in Moire Interferometry, Ph.D. dissertation, VPI&SU, (1984).
18. H. Ho, M.Y. Tsai, J. Morton and G.L. Farley, submitted to Experimental Mechanics.
19. H. Ho, M.Y. Tsai, J. Morton and G.L. Farley, to be submitted to Composite Science and Technology.

Figure 1. Test specimen dimensions for (a) 10° off-axis, (b) ±45° tension, (c) Iosipescu specimens.

Figure 2. Shear stress-strain data on the front (moire) and back (strain gage rosette) faces for 10° off-axis specimen.

Figure 3.
 (a) u-field and (b) v-field
 fringe patterns for the 10°
 off-axis specimen under
 22.1 MPa.

Figure 5.
 Shear stress-strain data on the front
 (moiré) and back (strain gage rosette)
 faces for $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile specimen.

Figure 4.
 Strain distributions (a) ϵ_1 , (b) ϵ_2
 and (c) γ_{12} at $y=0$ and $y=\pm w$
 (w =width of specimen), reduced
 from moiré fringe contours for
 the 10° off-axis specimen.

Figure 6. (a) u-field and (b) v-field fringe patterns for the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile specimen under 22.1 MPa.

Figure 7. Non-uniformity of v-field fringe pattern for the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile specimen under 55.2 MPa.

Figure 8. Strain distributions (a) ϵ_1 , (b) ϵ_2 and (c) γ_{12} at $y=0$ and $y=w/2$ (w =width of specimen), reduced from moire fringe contours for the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile specimen.

Figure 9. Shear stress-strain data obtained from front (moire) and back (strain gage rosette) faces of the 0° losipescu specimen.

Figure 10. Shear stress-strain data obtained from front (moire) and back (strain gage rosette) faces of the 90° losipescu specimen.

Figure 11. (a) u-field and (b) v-field fringe patterns for the 0° Iosipescu specimen under 20.5 MPa.

Figure 12. (a) u-field and (b) v-field fringe patterns for the 90° Iosipescu specimen under 20.5 MPa.

Figure 13. Typical shear stress-strain responses (a) before and (b) after the application of correction factors. Note that the end points of the shear stress-strain response curves do not indicate specimen failure.

